

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Orolova Shakhzoda Alisher qizi

Student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

Faculty: Foreign language and literature: English language

*Supervisor: **Shakirova Madina,***

Senior teacher, Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

Abstract: *Nowadays, in the world, the demand for effective foreign language education is being more important. Traditional methods of language instruction often fall short in meeting the needs of modern learners, prompting educators to explore innovative teaching strategies. This article examines a range of contemporary approaches that enhance language acquisition, including the integration of technology, gamification, task-based learning, project-based learning, which help to foster students knowledge, collaboration and they make easier children's or students' language learning process*

These methods not only improve linguistic skills but also foster learner motivation, engagement, and cultural competence and By adopting innovative techniques, language educators can create dynamic, student-centered learning environments that respond to diverse learning styles and the evolving demands of global communication.

Key words: *Innovative technologies , gamification , Task-based language teaching, Project-based learning to foster students knowledge, collaboration and language learning process*

Innovative teaching strategies are modern instructional methods that incorporate technology, interactive activities, and diverse resources to promote meaningful learning experiences. The aim of these approaches to actively involve students in the learning process, moving beyond traditional lectures and textbooks. They encourage learners to engage with content through hands-on exploration, thoughtful discussions, critical thinking, and teamwork. Such methods make learning more dynamic and enjoyable, offering multiple ways for students to connect with and understand the material more deeply. When students are encouraged to explore, analyze, and collaborate, they enhance essential skills like problem-solving and decision-making. Additionally, these strategies support peer collaboration by creating opportunities for students to work together on shared tasks and challenges. Implementing innovative teaching strategies can be challenging, but with the right resources and support, teachers can successfully incorporate them into their classrooms. It is important to start by understanding the different types of innovative teaching strategies so that you can determine which ones will work best for your students. Once you have determined which strategies are most appropriate for your classroom, it is essential to provide clear instructions and expectations for the students before beginning a project or

activity.

One of the most popular methods is learning with technology. There are many apps like Duolingo or Babbel that help students practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. These apps are easy to use and let students learn anytime and anywhere. With technology, learners can still experience some of the benefits of immersion. Thanks to next-generation messaging and social networks, remote students can access fluent speakers of the languages they are learning, offering real-world language practice that is not possible in traditional classrooms. Dynamic collaboration tools foster a sense of community along with interactive learning activities, allowing students to participate in class when it is convenient for them and removing barriers of space and time. In general, technology-enabled learning experiences encourage more consistent engagement among students, giving them access to peers and instructors around the clock and from anywhere in the world. Technology also offers dozens of tools to help learners in real time. Students can access simplified dictionaries, create flashcards, and browse the internet in the language they are learning. They can find pen pals, conversation partners, and online tutors. And they can encounter rich examples of the languages they are learning rather than being limited to static examples from traditional textbooks. Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, and Twitter all offer a daily language practice for foreign language learners who want to combine social media consumption with language learning practice.

Another effective way is gamification which is an approach where instructional materials are designed like games in order to make learning fun and engaging for students. In this method, students earn points, complete challenges, and compete with friends while learning. Gamification has become an innovative trend in education which aims to make the learning process more attractive to students in a fun and humorous learning environment and is believed to facilitate and encourage students to participate in learning.

Task-Based Learning (TBL) is a lesson structure, a method of sequencing activities in your lessons. Sometimes called ‘task-based language teaching’, in TBL lessons, students solve a task that involves an authentic use of language rather than complete simple questions about grammar or vocabulary. Task-based learning is an excellent way to get students engaged and using English. That, plus the collaborative element, builds confidence in language and social situations. It’s also been shown to align with how we learn a language. Task-based learning is also very helpful. This means students do real-world tasks in the foreign language, such as ordering food at a restaurant or planning a trip. This helps them use the language naturally and improves their speaking skills. During task-based learning, students solve tasks that are relevant and interesting to them. In order to solve the task, they need to use the target language they’re learning to communicate with their peers. They use authentic language instead of answering grammar or vocabulary questions about the language. Students — especially younger learners — don’t actually feel that they’re studying a language at

that moment because they're engrossed in the task they're working on. We can say as an example for task-based learning approach is designing your dream house, children should use vocabulary related to rooms, furniture, and describing places they discuss different types of houses and rooms then they design their own dream house on paper or using an app lastly, they present their house to the class, explaining each room and its features. teacher gives feedback and focuses on language used in their description

Project-based learning (PBL) or project-based instruction is an instructional approach designed to give students the opportunity to develop knowledge and skills through engaging projects set around challenges and problems they may face in the real world. Project-based learning is more than just "doing a project," in the way you might remember from your own school days. As the Buck Institute for Education (BIE) explains, with PBL, students "investigate and respond to an authentic, engaging, and complex problem or challenge" with deep and sustained attention.¹ ArchForKids, an organization that provides STEAM programs for young learners, puts it even more succinctly: PBL is "learning by doing." for example, creating a presentation, making a video or short movie, writing a piece of text, such as a newsletter article.

In conclusion, Innovative teaching strategies are essential for creating an engaging and effective learning environment for students. They help teachers to develop creative approaches to instruction, as well as help students become independent learners. By providing a variety of different instructional strategies and materials, teachers can boost student engagement and achievement in the classroom.

References

1. Ebadi, S., Rasouli, R., and Mohamadi, M. (2021). Exploring EFL learners' perspectives on using Kahoot as a game-based student response system. *Interact. Learn. Environ.* 1–13. doi: 10.1080/10494820.2021.1881798
2. <https://strobelededucation.com>
3. <https://www.powerschool.com>
4. <https://www.barefootteflteacher.com>